

Versioned Archive and Review of Biotic
Interactions and Taxon Names Found within
globalbioticinteractions/maate
hash://md5/aea4c7e89ecce41e721049675ac6bd10

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Abstract

Life on Earth is sustained by complex interactions between organisms and their environment. These biotic interactions can be captured in datasets and published digitally. We present a review and archiving process for such an openly accessible digital interactions dataset of known origin and discuss its outcome. The dataset under review, named globalbioticinteractions/maate, has fingerprint hash://md5/aea4c7e89ecce41e721049675ac6bd10, is 101MiB in size and contains 686 interactions with 6 unique types of associations (e.g., adjacentTo) between 197 primary taxa (e.g., *Bos taurus*) and 274 associated taxa (e.g., *Bos taurus*). This report includes detailed summaries of interaction data, a taxonomic review from multiple catalogs, and an archived version of the dataset from which the reviews are derived.

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Introduction

Data Review and Archive

Data review and archiving can be a time-consuming process, especially when done manually. This review report aims to help facilitate both activities. It automates the archiving of datasets, including Darwin Core archives, and is a citable backup of a version of the dataset. Additionally, an automatic review of species interaction claims made in the dataset is generated and registered with Global Biotic Interactions (J. H. Poelen, Simons, and Mungall 2014).

This review includes summary statistics about, and observations about, the dataset under review :

Banco de Vida/ CJ Museum/ Amphibian collection - Version 2.1
http://patrimonio.ambiente.gob.ec/iptmae/archive.do?r=cj_bancovida_museo2026-06-02T16:44:15.552Z Characterization of Microbiological and Invertebrate Biodiversity in the El Pelado Marine Reserve (REMAPE) at the Taxonomic, Metabolomic, and Metagenomic Levels for Use in Human and Animal Health. - Version 2.3
http://patrimonio.ambiente.gob.ec/iptmae/archive.do?r=inmase_ce2026-06-02T16:44:15.552Z Colección de Anfibios del Museo de Zoología QCAZ - Version 1.3 <http://patrimonio.ambiente.gob.ec/iptmae/archive.do?r=a5a6e882-b3ce-4e24-b337-33b4295d06202026-06-02T16:44:15.552Z> Colección de Ornitología del Instituto Nacional de Biodiversidad - Version 2.3
<http://patrimonio.ambiente.gob.ec/iptmae/archive.do?r=3e52fb9c-1a90-4c3c-bc7e-eca3122e05e82026-06-02T16:44:15.552Z> Colección de Plantas Vasculares del Herbario UTCEC - Version 2.1
<http://patrimonio.ambiente.gob.ec/iptmae/archive.do?r=utcecvasculares2026-06-02T16:44:15.552Z> Colección de Reptiles del Museo de Zoología QCAZ - Version 1.1 <http://patrimonio.ambiente.gob.ec/iptmae/archive.do?r=84c3ac72f3d-4f8a-bb24-129300b030ca2026-06-02T16:44:15.552Z> Colección

de Vertebrados Estación Científica Charles Darwin - Version 2.0
<http://patrimonio.ambiente.gob.ec/iptmae/archive.do?r=vccdrs>
 2026-06-02T16:44:15.552Z Colección Marina Estación Científica
 Charles Darwin - Version 2.0 <http://patrimonio.ambiente.gob.ec/iptmae/archive.do?r=mccdrs>
 2026-06-02T16:44:15.552Z Registros de conflicto humano-
 fauna en Ecuador desde el año 2009 al 2022 - Version 1.4
[http://patrimonio.ambiente.gob.ec/iptmae/archive.do?r=humano-](http://patrimonio.ambiente.gob.ec/iptmae/archive.do?r=humano-fauna)
 fauna 2026-06-02T16:44:15.552Z hash://md5/aea4c7e89ecce41e721049675ac6bd10

Methods

The review is performed through programmatic scripts that leverage tools like Preston (Elliott et al. 2025), Elton (Kuhn, Poelen, and Leinweber 2025), Nomer (Salim and Poelen 2025), globinizer (J. Poelen, Seltmann, and Mietchen 2024) combined with third-party tools like grep, mlr, tail and head.

Table 1: Tools used in this review process

tool name	version
preston	0.11.1
elton	0.16.11
nomer	0.6.5
globinizer	0.4.0
mlr	6.0.0
jq	1.6
yq	4.25.3
pandoc	3.1.6.1
duckdb	1.3.1
mapserver	7.6.4

The review process can be described in the form of the script below ¹.

```
# get versioned copy of the dataset (size approx. 101MiB) under review
elton pull globalbioticinteractions/maate

# generate review notes
elton review globalbioticinteractions/maate \
  > review.tsv

# export indexed interaction records
```

¹Note that you have to first get the data (e.g., via `elton pull globalbioticinteractions/maate`) before being able to generate reviews (e.g., `elton review globalbioticinteractions/maate`), extract interaction claims (e.g., `elton interactions globalbioticinteractions/maate`), or list taxonomic names (e.g., `elton names globalbioticinteractions/maate`)

```

elton interactions globalbioticinteractions/maate \
> interactions.tsv

# export names and align them with the Catalogue of Life using Nomer
elton names globalbioticinteractions/maate \
| nomer append col \
> name-alignment.tsv

```

or visually, in a process diagram.

Figure 1: Review Process Overview

You can find a copy of the full review script at `check-data.sh`. See also GitHub and Codeberg.

Results

In the following sections, the results of the review are summarized ². Then, links to the detailed review reports are provided.

Files

An extensive list of files produced as part of the review process can be found in Appendix A. Review Files.

Archived Dataset

Note that `data.zip` file in this archive contains the complete, unmodified archived dataset under review.

Biotic Interactions

In this review, biotic interactions (or biotic associations) are modeled as a primary (aka subject, source) organism interacting with an associate (aka object, target) organism. The dataset under review classified the primary/associate organisms with specific taxa. The primary and associate organisms The kind of interaction is documented as an interaction type.

²Disclaimer: The results in this review should be considered friendly, yet naive, notes from an unsophisticated robot. Please keep that in mind when considering the review results.

Figure 2: Biotic Interaction Data Model

The dataset under review, named `globalbioticinteractions/maate`, has fingerprint hash://md5/aea4c7e89ecce41e721049675ac6bd10, is 101MiB in size and contains 686 interactions with 6 unique types of associations (e.g., `adjacentTo`) between 197 primary taxa (e.g., `Bos taurus`) and 274 associated taxa (e.g., `Bos taurus`).

An exhaustive list of indexed interaction claims can be found in gzipped `csv`, `tsv`, `geopackage` and `parquet` archives. To facilitate discovery, a preview of claims available in the gzipped `html` page at `indexed-interactions.html.gz` are shown below.

The exhaustive list was used to create the following data summaries below.

Table 2: Sample of Indexed Interaction Claims

sourceTaxonName	interactionTypeName	targetTaxonName	referenceCitation
Aplysina	interactsWith	Chordata	150813EP07-10
Ascidia	interactsWith	Chordata	150924EP01-04
Didemnum	interactsWith	Chordata	150924EP07-04
Muricea austera	interactsWith	Didemnum sp.	160212EP13-02

Table 3: Most Frequently Mentioned Interaction Types (up to 20 most frequent)

interactionTypeName	count
adjacentTo	299
preysOn	163
preyedUponBy	163
interactsWith	33
hasHost	22
killedBy	6

Table 4: Most Frequently Mentioned Primary Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

sourceTaxonName	count
Bos taurus	108
Tremarctos ornatus	82
Puma concolor	41
Panthera onca	29
Pristimantis Indeterminado	21
Ovis aries	21
Pristimantis andinognomus	13
Engystomops petersi	12
Lynchius Indeterminado	9
Pristimantis brevicrus	8
Rhinella acutirostris	8
Anolis fuscoauratus	7
Pristimantis sternothylax	7
Anolis scypheus	6
Anolis aequatorialis	6
Anolis peraccae	6
Scinax tsachila	5
Pristimantis lanthanites	5
Osteocephalus mutabor	5

Table 5: Most Frequently Mentioned Associate Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

targetTaxonName	count
Bos taurus	108
Tremarctos ornatus	82
Puma concolor	41
Panthera onca	29
the ground	21
Ovis aries	21
the road	10
crosses in lab	7
leaf	6
vegetation at 10-20 cm	6
Chordata	5
tree	5
a leaf at 30 cm	5
Cnidarian	4
a leaf at 50 cm	4

targetTaxonName	count
log	4
vehicle	4
a leaf at 60 cm	4
the ground in leaf litter	4

Table 6: Most Frequent Interactions between Primary and Associate Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

sourceTaxonName	interactionType	targetTaxonName	count
Tremarctos ornatus	preysOn	Bos taurus	70
Bos taurus	preyedUponBy	Tremarctos ornatus	70
Panthera onca	preysOn	Bos taurus	24
Bos taurus	preyedUponBy	Panthera onca	24
Puma concolor	preysOn	Ovis aries	21
Ovis aries	preyedUponBy	Puma concolor	21
Puma concolor	preysOn	Bos taurus	8
Bos taurus	preyedUponBy	Puma concolor	8
Engystomops petersi	interactsWith	crosses in lab	7
Epipedobates anthonyi	adjacentTo	the ground	5
Pristimantis Indeterminado	adjacentTo	vegetation at 10-20 cm	4
Tremarctos ornatus	preysOn	Bos spp	4
Bos spp	preyedUponBy	Tremarctos ornatus	4
Scinax tsachila	adjacentTo	branches and leaves of scrub 1m above ground	3
Allobates femoralis	adjacentTo	ground (mud)	3
Pristimantis malkini	adjacentTo	leaf	3
Pristimantis andinognomus	adjacentTo	a leaf at 60 cm	3
Lynchius Indeterminado	adjacentTo	the ground in leaf litter	3
Pristimantis Indeterminado	adjacentTo	the ground	3

Interaction Networks

The figures below provide a graph view on the dataset under review. The first shows a summary network on the kingdom level, and the second shows how interactions on the family level. It is important to note that both network graphs were first aligned taxonomically using the Catalogue of Life. Please refer to the original (or verbatim) taxonomic names for a more original view on the interaction data.

Figure 3: Interactions on taxonomic kingdom rank as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life download `svg`

You can download the indexed dataset under review at `indexed-interactions.csv.gz`. A tab-separated file can be found at `indexed-interactions.tsv.gz`

Geospatial Distribution

If geospatial information was extracted from the dataset under review, the map below will show their distribution. These maps were generated using MapServer (McKenna et al. 2025) tools configured via map configuration `indexed-interactions.map` :

```
MAP
  SIZE 1600 800
  EXTENT -180 -90 180 90
  PROJECTION
    "init=epsg:4326"
  END
  LAYER # MODIS WMS map from NASA
    NAME "modis_nasa"
    TYPE RASTER
    OFFSITE 0 0 0
    STATUS ON
    CONNECTIONTYPE WMS
    CONNECTION "https://gibs.earthdata.nasa.gov/wms/epsg4326/best/wms.cgi?"
```


Figure 4: Interactions on the taxonomic family rank as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life. [download svg](#)

```

METADATA
  "wms_srs" "EPSG:4326"
  "wms_name" "OSM_Land_Water_Map"
  "wms_server_version" "1.1.1"
  "wms_format" "image/jpeg"
END
CLASS
  STYLE
    COLOR          232 232 232
    OUTLINECOLOR  32 32 32
  END
END
LAYER
  NAME "indexed-interactions"
  TYPE POLYGON
  STATUS ON
  CONNECTIONTYPE OGR
  CONNECTION "indexed-interactions-h3.gpkg"
  DATA "indexed-interactions-h3"
  CLASS
    STYLE
      COLORRANGE 253.0 231.0 37.0 32.0 164.0 134.0
      DATARANGE 0.9030899869919435 2.2576785748691846
      RANGEITEM "log_number_of_records"
      OUTLINECOLOR 0 0 0
    END
  END
END

```

Associated data can be found in the geopackage files at indexed-interactions.gpkg for point data and indexed-interactions-h3.gpkg for data clustered in geospatial h3 hexagonals.

Learn more about the structure of this download at GloBI website, by opening a GitHub issue, or by sending an email.

Another way to discover the dataset under review is by searching for it on the GloBI website.

Taxonomic Alignment

As part of the review, all names are aligned against various name catalogs (e.g., col, ncbi, discoverlife, gbif, itis, wfo, mdd, tpt, pbdb, and worms). These alignments can help review name usage or aid in selecting of a suitable taxonomic name resource.

Figure 5: Hexagonal grid cells indicate that interactions claims are available for selected geospatial area: light yellow means relatively fewer claims, dark green relatively more claims.

Table 7: Sample of Name Alignments

providedName	relationName	resolvedCatalogName	resolvedName
Vernonanthura patens	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	col	Vernonanthura patens
Del suelo	NONE	col	Del suelo
Peperomia	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	col	Peperomia
Monnina herbacea	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	col	Monnina herbacea

Table 8: Distribution of Taxonomic Ranks of Aligned Names by Catalog. Names that were not aligned with a catalog are counted as NAs. So, the total number of unaligned names for a catalog will be listed in their NA row.

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
col	NA	167
col	genus	20
col	kingdom	1
col	phylum	6
col	species	167
col	subgenus	1
col	subspecies	4

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
discoverlife	NA	364
discoverlife	species	1
gbif	NA	170
gbif	genus	20
gbif	kingdom	1
gbif	phylum	6
gbif	species	163
gbif	subspecies	5
itis	NA	180
itis	genus	18
itis	kingdom	1
itis	phylum	6
itis	species	154
itis	subspecies	5
mdd	NA	364
ncbi	NA	187
ncbi	genus	19
ncbi	kingdom	1
ncbi	phylum	6
ncbi	species	149
ncbi	subgenus	1
ncbi	subspecies	3
pbdb	NA	323
pbdb	genus	8
pbdb	kingdom	1
pbdb	phylum	6
pbdb	species	26
pbdb	unranked clade	1
tpt	NA	342
tpt	genus	4
tpt	species	18
wfo	NA	356
wfo	genus	4
wfo	phylum	1
wfo	species	3
worms	NA	327
worms	genus	12
worms	kingdom	1
worms	phylum	6
worms	species	18

Table 9: Name relationship types per catalog. Name relationship type “NONE” means that a name was not recognized by the associated catalog. “SAME_AS” indicates either a “HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME” or “SYNONYM_OF” name relationship type. We recognize that “SYNONYM_OF” encompasses many types of nomenclatural synonymies (ICZN 1999) (e.g., junior synonym, senior synonyms).

resolvedCatalogName	relationName	count
col	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	229
col	NONE	231
col	SYNONYM_OF	14
discoverlife	NONE	470
discoverlife	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	1
gbif	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	242
gbif	NONE	236
gbif	SYNONYM_OF	17
itis	NONE	246
itis	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	210
itis	SYNONYM_OF	6
mdd	NONE	422
mdd	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	40
ncbi	SAME_AS	204
ncbi	NONE	261
ncbi	SYNONYM_OF	7
pbdb	NONE	394
pbdb	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	69
pbdb	SYNONYM_OF	6
tpt	NONE	416
tpt	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	46
wfo	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	7
wfo	NONE	453
wfo	SYNONYM_OF	1
wfo	HAS_UNCHECKED_NAME	1
worms	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	54
worms	NONE	408
worms	SYNONYM_OF	2

Table 10: List of Available Name Alignment Reports

catalog name	alignment results
col	associated names alignments report in zipped html, csv, and tsv)

catalog name	alignment results
ncbi	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
discoverlife	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
gbif	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
itis	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
wfo	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
mdd	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
tpt	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
pbdb	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
worms	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)

Additional Reviews

Elton, Nomer, and other tools may have difficulties interpreting existing species interaction datasets. Or, they may misbehave, or otherwise show unexpected behavior. As part of the review process, detailed review notes are kept that document possibly misbehaving, or confused, review bots. An sample of review notes associated with this review can be found below.

reviewDate	reviewCommentType	reviewComment
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Table 11: First few lines in the review notes.

reviewDate	reviewCommentType	reviewComment
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2026-06-03T18:53:46Z	note	<pre> [] Caused by: org.eol.globi.data.StudyImporterException: failed to read archive [http://patrimonio.ambiente.gob.ec/iptmae/archive.do? 6862-4a34-9bb6- c1fc9e3fa99d] at org.eol.globi.data.DatasetImporterForDwCA.importStu at org.eol.globi.util.DatasetImportUtil.importDataset(Dat at org.eol.globi.util.DatasetImportUtil.importDataset(Dat at org.eol.globi.util.DatasetImportUtil.indexDatasets(Dat at org.eol.globi.util.DatasetImportUtil.indexUnresolvedDe at org.eol.globi.util.DatasetImportUtil.resolveAndImportD at org.eol.globi.data.DatasetImporterForRSS.importStudy at org.eol.globi.util.DatasetImportUtil.importDataset(Dat at org.globalbioticinteractions.elton.cmd.CmdReview.revie at org.globalbioticinteractions.elton.cmd.CmdReview.revie at org.globalbioticinteractions.elton.cmd.CmdReview.doRu at org.globalbioticinteractions.elton.cmd.CmdDefaultParam at org.globalbioticinteractions.elton.cmd.CmdTabularWrit at pico- cli.CommandLine.executeUserObject(CommandLine.java: at picocli.CommandLine.access1300(CommandLine.java: 145)atpicocli.CommandLineRunLast.executeUserObjec at picocli.CommandLineRunLast.handle(CommandLine.java: 2352)atpicocli.CommandLineRunLast.handle(Command at picocli.CommandLineAbstractParseResultHandler.ex 2179)atpicocli.CommandLineRunLast.execute(Command at pico- cli.CommandLine.execute(CommandLine.java:2078) at org.globalbioticinteractions.elton.Elton.run(Elton.java:1 at org.globalbioticinteractions.elton.Elton.main(Elton.java: Caused by: java.io.IOException: resource </pre>
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reviewDate	reviewCommentType	reviewComment
2026-06-03T18:54:56Z	note	<pre> [] Caused by: org.eol.globi.data.StudyImporterException: failed to read archive [http://patrimonio.ambiente.gob.ec/iptmae/archive.do? 6862-4a34-9bb6- c1fc9e3fa99d] at org.eol.globi.data.DatasetImporterForDwCA.importStu at org.eol.globi.util.DatasetImportUtil.importDataset(Dat at org.eol.globi.util.DatasetImportUtil.importDataset(Dat at org.eol.globi.util.DatasetImportUtil.indexDatasets(Data at org.eol.globi.util.DatasetImportUtil.resolveDependencies at org.eol.globi.util.DatasetImportUtil.resolveAndImportD at org.eol.globi.data.DatasetImporterForRSS.importStudy at org.eol.globi.util.DatasetImportUtil.importDataset(Dat at org.globalbioticinteractions.elton.cmd.CmdReview.review at org.globalbioticinteractions.elton.cmd.CmdReview.review at org.globalbioticinteractions.elton.cmd.CmdReview.doRu at org.globalbioticinteractions.elton.cmd.CmdDefaultParam at org.globalbioticinteractions.elton.cmd.CmdTabularWrit at pico- cli.CommandLine.executeUserObject(CommandLine.java at picocli.CommandLine.access1300(CommandLine.java: 145)atpicocli.CommandLineRunLast.executeUserObject at picocli.CommandLineRunLast.handle(CommandLine. 2352)atpicocli.CommandLineRunLast.handle(Comm at picocli.CommandLineAbstractParseResultHandler.ex 2179)atpicocli.CommandLineRunLast.execute(Comm at pico- cli.CommandLine.execute(CommandLine.java:2078) at org.globalbioticinteractions.elton.Elton.run(Elton.java:1 at org.globalbioticinteractions.elton.Elton.main(Elton.java Caused by: java.io.IOException: resource [http://patrimonio.ambiente.gob.ec/iptmae/archive.do? 6862-4a34-9bb6- c1fc9e3fa99d] not found </pre>

reviewDate	reviewCommentType	reviewComment
2026-06-03T18:55:54Z	note	found unresolved reference [44a8e8e7-16de-4897- a1cb-7af5aa838733]
2026-06-03T18:55:54Z	note	found unresolved reference [6ec4323f-1bd7-49f8- a9a8-9dc1db45b137]

In addition, you can find the most frequently occurring notes in the table below.

reviewComment	count
---------------	-------

Table 12: Most frequently occurring review notes, if any.

reviewComment	count
---------------	-------

<p>[] Caused by: org.eol.globi.data.StudyImporterException: failed to read archive [http://patrimonio.ambiente.gob.ec/iptmae/archive.do?r=b52174ab-6862-4a34-9bb6-c1fc9e3fa99d] at org.eol.globi.data.DatasetImporterForDwCA.importStudy(DatasetImporterForDwCA.java:365) at org.eol.globi.util.DatasetImportUtil.importDataset(DatasetImportUtil.java:71) at org.eol.globi.util.DatasetImportUtil.importDataset(DatasetImportUtil.java:42) at org.eol.globi.util.DatasetImportUtil.indexDatasets(DatasetImportUtil.java:160) at org.eol.globi.util.DatasetImportUtil.indexUnresolvedDependencies(DatasetImportUtil.java:117) at org.eol.globi.util.DatasetImportUtil.resolveAndImportDatasets(DatasetImportUtil.java:84) at org.eol.globi.data.DatasetImporterForRSS.importStudy(DatasetImporterForRSS.java:45) at org.eol.globi.util.DatasetImportUtil.importDataset(DatasetImportUtil.java:71) at org.globalbioticinteractions.elton.cmd.CmdReview.review(CmdReview.java:259) at org.globalbioticinteractions.elton.cmd.CmdReview.reviewLocal(CmdReview.java:212) at org.globalbioticinteractions.elton.cmd.CmdReview.doRun(CmdReview.java:147) at org.globalbioticinteractions.elton.cmd.CmdDefaultParams.run(CmdDefaultParams.java:223) at org.globalbioticinteractions.elton.cmd.CmdTabularWriterParams.run(CmdTabularWriterParams.java:12) at pico- cli.CommandLine.executeUserObject(CommandLine.java:1939) at picocli.CommandLine.access1300(<i>CommandLine.java</i> : 145)<i>atpicocli.CommandLineRunLast.executeUserObjectOfLastSubcommandWithSameParent</i>(CommandLine at picocli.CommandLineRunLast.handle(<i>CommandLine.java</i> : 2352)<i>atpicocli.CommandLineRunLast.handle</i>(CommandLine.java:2314) at picocli.CommandLineAbstractParseResultHandler.execute(<i>CommandLine.java</i> : 2179)<i>atpicocli.CommandLineRunLast.execute</i>(CommandLine.java:2316) at pico- cli.CommandLine.execute(CommandLine.java:2078) at org.globalbioticinteractions.elton.Elton.run(Elton.java:110) at org.globalbioticinteractions.elton.Elton.main(Elton.java:94) Caused by: java.io.IOException: resource [http://patrimonio.ambiente.gob.ec/iptmae/archive.do?r=b52174ab-6862-4a34-9bb6-c1fc9e3fa99d].not</p>	1
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reviewComment	count
<pre> [] Caused by: org.eol.globi.data.StudyImporterException: failed to read archive [http://patrimonio.ambiente.gob.ec/iptmae/archive.do?r=b52174ab- 6862-4a34-9bb6-c1fc9e3fa99d] at org.eol.globi.data.DatasetImporterForDwCA.importStudy(DatasetImporterForDwCA.java:365) at org.eol.globi.util.DatasetImportUtil.importDataset(DatasetImportUtil.java:71) at org.eol.globi.util.DatasetImportUtil.importDataset(DatasetImportUtil.java:42) at org.eol.globi.util.DatasetImportUtil.indexDatasets(DatasetImportUtil.java:160) at org.eol.globi.util.DatasetImportUtil.resolveDependencies(DatasetImportUtil.java:104) at org.eol.globi.util.DatasetImportUtil.resolveAndImportDatasets(DatasetImportUtil.java:86) at org.eol.globi.data.DatasetImporterForRSS.importStudy(DatasetImporterForRSS.java:45) at org.eol.globi.util.DatasetImportUtil.importDataset(DatasetImportUtil.java:71) at org.globalbioticinteractions.elton.cmd.CmdReview.review(CmdReview.java:259) at org.globalbioticinteractions.elton.cmd.CmdReview.reviewLocal(CmdReview.java:212) at org.globalbioticinteractions.elton.cmd.CmdReview.doRun(CmdReview.java:147) at org.globalbioticinteractions.elton.cmd.CmdDefaultParams.run(CmdDefaultParams.java:223) at org.globalbioticinteractions.elton.cmd.CmdTabularWriterParams.run(CmdTabularWriterParams.java:12) at pico- cli.CommandLine.executeUserObject(CommandLine.java:1939) at picocli.CommandLine.access1300(CommandLine.java : 145)atpicocli.CommandLineRunLast.executeUserObjectOfLastSubcommandWithSameParent(CommandLine at picocli.CommandLineRunLast.handle(CommandLine.java : 2352)atpicocli.CommandLineRunLast.handle(CommandLine.java:2314) at picocli.CommandLineAbstractParseResultHandler.execute(CommandLine.java : 2179)atpicocli.CommandLineRunLast.execute(CommandLine.java:2316) at pico- cli.CommandLine.execute(CommandLine.java:2078) at org.globalbioticinteractions.elton.Elton.run(Elton.java:110) at org.globalbioticinteractions.elton.Elton21main(Elton.java:94) Caused by: java.io.IOException: resource [http://patrimonio.ambiente.gob.ec/iptmae/archive.do?r=b52174ab- 6862-4a34-9bb6-c1fc9e3fa99d] not found at [http://patrimonio.ambiente.gob.ec/iptmae/archive.do?r=b52174ab- 6862-4a34-9bb6-c1fc9e3fa99d] at </pre>	1

reviewComment	count
found unresolved reference [44a8e8e7-16de-4897-a1cb-7af5aa838733]	1
found unresolved reference [6ec4323f-1bd7-49f8-a9a8-9dc1db45b137]	1

For additional information on review notes, please have a look at the first 500 Review Notes in html format or the download full gzipped csv or tsv archives.

GloBI Review Badge

As part of the review, a review badge is generated. This review badge can be included in webpages to indicate the review status of the dataset under review.

Figure 6: Picture of a GloBI Review Badge ³

Note that if the badge is green, no review notes were generated. If the badge is yellow, the review bots may need some help with interpreting the species interaction data.

GloBI Index Badge

If the dataset under review has been registered with GloBI, and has been successfully indexed by GloBI, the GloBI Index Status Badge will turn green. This means that the dataset under review was indexed by GloBI and is available through GloBI services and derived data products.

Figure 7: Picture of a GloBI Index Badge ⁴

If you'd like to keep track of reviews or index status of the dataset under review, please visit GloBI's dataset index ⁵ for badge examples.

Discussion

This review and archive provides a means of creating citable versions of datasets that change frequently. This may be useful for dataset managers, including

³Up-to-date status of the GloBI Review Badge can be retrieved from the GloBI Review Depot

⁴Up-to-date status of the GloBI Index Badge can be retrieved from GloBI's API

⁵At time of writing (2026-06-03) the version of the GloBI dataset index was available at <https://globalbioticinteractions.org/datasets>

natural history collection data managers, as a backup archive of a shared Darwin Core archive. It also serves as a means of creating a trackable citation for the dataset in an automated way, while also including some information about the contents of the dataset.

This review aims to provide a perspective on the dataset to aid in understanding of species interaction claims discovered. However, it is important to note that this review does *not* assess the quality of the dataset. Instead, it serves as an indication of the open-ness⁶ and FAIRness (Wilkinson et al. 2016; Trekels et al. 2023) of the dataset: to perform this review, the data was likely openly available, **F**indable, **A**ccessible, **I**nteroperable and **R**eusable. The current Open-FAIR assessment is qualitative, and a more quantitative approach can be implemented with specified measurement units.

This report also showcases the reuse of machine-actionable (meta)data, something highly recommended by the FAIR Data Principles (Wilkinson et al. 2016). Making (meta)data machine-actionable enables more precise processing by computers, enabling even naive review bots like Nomer and Elton to interpret the data effectively. This capability is crucial for not just automating the generation of reports, but also for facilitating seamless data exchanges, promoting interoperability.

Acknowledgements

We thank the many humans that created us and those who created and maintained the data, software and other intellectual resources that were used for producing this review. In addition, we are grateful for the natural resources providing the basis for these human and bot activities. Also, thanks to <https://github.com/zygoballus> for helping improve the layout of the review tables.

Author contributions

Nomer was responsible for name alignments. Elton carried out dataset extraction, and generated the review notes. Preston tracked, versioned, and packaged, the dataset under review.

Appendix A. Review Files

The following files are produced in this review:

⁶According to <http://opendefinition.org/>: “Open data is data that can be freely used, reused and redistributed by anyone - subject only, at most, to the requirement to attribute and sharealike.”

filename	description
biblio.bib	list of bibliographic reference of this review
check-dataset.sh	data review workflow/process as expressed in a bash script
data.zip	a versioned archive of the data under review
HEAD	the digital signature of the data under review
index.docx	review in MS Word format
index.html	review in HTML format
index.md	review in Pandoc markdown format
index.pdf	review in PDF format
indexed-citations.csv.gz	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interaction claims in gzipped comma-separated values file format
indexed-citations.html.gz	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interactions claims in gzipped html file format
indexed-citations.tsv.gz	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interaction claims in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-interactions-col-family-col-family.svg	network diagram showing the taxon family to taxon family interaction claims in the dataset under review as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life via Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024)
indexed-interactions-col-kingdom-col-kingdom.svg	network diagram showing the taxon kingdom to taxon kingdom interaction claims in the dataset under review as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life via Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024)
indexed-interactions.csv.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-interactions.html.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped html format
indexed-interactions.tsv.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-interactions.parquet	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in Apache Parquet format
indexed-interactions.png	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review plotted on a map
indexed-interactions.map	mapserver configuration to plot species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review on a map
indexed-interactions.gpkg	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in GeoPackage format
indexed-interactions-h3.gpkg	geospatially clustered h3 species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in GeoPackage format
indexed-interactions-sample.csv	list of species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-interactions-sample.html	first 500 species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in html format
indexed-interactions-sample.tsv	first 500 species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in tab-separated values format
indexed-names.csv.gz	taxonomic names indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in gzipped html format
indexed-names.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in Apache Parquet format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-col.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-col.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-col.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-col.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-itis.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-worms.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-sample.csv	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in comma-separated values format
indexed-names-sample.html	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in html format
indexed-names-sample.tsv	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in tab-separated values format
interaction.svg	diagram summarizing the data model used to index species interaction claims
nanopub-sample.trig	first 500 species interaction claims as expressed in the nanopub format (Kuhn and Dumontier 2014)

filename	description
nanopub.trig.gz	species interaction claims as expressed in the nanopub format (Kuhn and Dumontier 2014)
process.svg	diagram summarizing the data review processing workflow
prov.nq	origin of the dataset under review as expressed in rdf/nquads
review.csv.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
review.html.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped html format
review.tsv.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format
review-sample.csv	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in comma-separated values format
review-sample.html	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in html format
review-sample.tsv	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in tab-separated values format
review.svg	a review badge generated as part of the dataset review process
zenodo.json	metadata of this review expressed in Zenodo record metadata

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